

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Comparison of Pb, Cd, Zn and Cr content of some mineral concrete admixtures

Oguzhan Yavuz BAYRAKTAR ^{1,*}, Aydin TURKYILMAZ ², Kaan ISINKARALAR ² and Gokhan KAPLAN ³

¹ Department of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Engineering and Architecture, Kastamonu University, Türkiye.

² Department of Environmental Engineering, Faculty of Engineering and Architecture, Kastamonu University, Türkiye.

³ Department of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Atatürk University, Türkiye.

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Abstract

Today, the demand for urban areas due to population growth worldwide and migration from rural to urban areas increases the need for new residential areas and new housing construction. This need also increases the demand for concrete, which is an important raw material especially in the building sector and constitutes a significant portion of construction input costs. Therefore, studies on the use of various environmental wastes as concrete admixtures in order to both reduce the cost of concrete and to dispose of environmental wastes are gaining importance and many studies have been conducted on the subject in recent years. However, the lack of sufficient data on the chemical structure of concrete admixtures leads to a lack of information on the environmental impacts of construction activities as well as the health of people working in the sector. For these reasons, this study aimed to determine and compare the Pb, Cr, Cd and Zn contents of some materials used as concrete admixtures. As a result of the study, it was determined that these heavy metal contents can vary significantly on a material basis and can reach up to 37.36 ppm for Pb, 103.67 ppm for Cr, 446.18 ppm for Zn and 444.85 ppm for Cd. This result shows that workers in the sector working with these materials may face serious health problems. Therefore, it is necessary to take precautions by providing the necessary awareness.

Keywords: Concrete; Admixture; Chemical Content; Heavy metal

1. Introduction

Both increasing population and migration from rural to urban areas necessitate the creation of new residential areas in urban centers and therefore the construction of new buildings [1-3]. Concrete is the basic building block of most of the high-rise buildings designed to accommodate more people per unit area. Concrete, which is formed by combining cement, aggregate, water and some additives when necessary, is used in a wide variety of structures in our age [4-6]. Concrete is used so intensively today that it is stated to be the most consumed building material in the world after water [7-9].

Therefore, concrete, which is used in such large quantities, causes the resources used as raw materials to be extracted from underground deposits and released into the nature, sometimes over a long period of time. Considering how many buildings are being constructed and how many of them have a lifespan limited to 20-30 years, it will be better understood how big a role the construction industry plays in the cycle of many elements and how much raw materials it requires. In fact, concrete production uses about 18% of the global annual industrial water use. In addition, it is stated that approximately 10% of global carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions are caused by cement production, which is the primary material of concrete production [10-16].

Especially in construction activities in urban centers, the amount of particulate matter in the air is significantly affected and increased during both construction and demolition phases [17]. The chemical structure of these particulate matter

* Corresponding author: Oguzhan Yavuz BAYRAKTAR

also affects environmental pollution. Environmental pollution, and especially air pollution, is shown as one of the most important global problems in the current century [17-26]. It is stated that air pollution has reached a dimension that will affect even the most remote ecosystems [27-29], and especially threatens human life seriously. In fact, it is reported that approximately 90% of the world's population now breathe polluted air, 99% are exposed to poor air quality, and air pollution causes approximately 6 million premature births, approximately 3 million underweight babies and approximately 7 million premature deaths worldwide every year [30-33].

The most important and harmful components of air pollution are heavy metals. Heavy metals, some of which are threatening to human health even at low concentrations, can cause very serious health problems such as cancer, respiratory diseases, heart attacks and even death [34-37]. Heavy metals can be even more harmful and fatal when they are inhaled into the human body [38]. Therefore, international organizations such as EPA and ATSDR have placed some heavy metals on the priority pollutant list [39-41]. It is of great importance for human health that these heavy metals do not exceed certain concentrations.

Various raw materials used in construction activities such as cement, sand, gypsum and bricks may contain high amounts of heavy metals. In addition, many additives used in recent years to reduce the cost of concrete are also reported to contain high amounts of heavy metals [42,43]. Many admixtures such as kiln slag, marble dust, brick dust, wood ash, silica fume can be substituted into concrete in order to prevent waste of resources by recycling and to reduce the cost of concrete [44-52]. However, there are very few studies on the heavy metal content of these admixtures. However, it is important to know the heavy metal contents of concrete admixtures both in terms of determining which heavy metals are eliminated by the use of these concrete admixtures, i.e. which heavy metals are eliminated as environmental pollutants, and how much these admixtures threaten human and environmental health. In this study, the contents of the ten most commonly used concrete admixtures were analyzed and the concentrations of Pb, Cr, Cd and Zn were compared. These heavy metals were chosen because they are both the most widely used and are on the priority pollutant list of EPA and ATSDR due to their potential hazards.

2. Material and methods

The aim of this study is to compare the chemical contents of some concrete mineral admixtures. For this purpose, some of the most commonly used mineral admixtures were selected as concrete raw materials. The concrete admixtures examined within the scope of the study are as follows;

- Fly ash
- Wood ash
- Silica fume
- Red Pumice
- Vermiculite
- Brick powder
- Tire powder
- Marble powder
- Zeolite
- Blast furnace slag

The materials obtained within the scope of the study were first prepared for preliminary analysis. The materials obtained at this stage were ground and sieved, then kept for about two weeks until room dry and then dried in an oven at 45 °C for two weeks. Then laboratory analyzes were carried out.

Elemental analyses were sent to Kastamonu University Central Research Laboratory Application and Research Center and performed with the help of ICP-OES device. Before elemental analysis, the dried samples were subjected to pre-incineration in a microwave oven specially designed for this process. The pre-burning samples were analyzed by ICP-OES to determine the concentrations of Pb, Cr, Cd and Zn and the heavy metal concentrations were calculated by multiplying the obtained values by the dilution factor. This method has been widely used in previous studies in this field [53,54]. The data obtained were analyzed using SPSS 22.0 package program and analysis of variance was applied to the data and Duncan test was applied for the factors showing statistically significant differences at a minimum 95% confidence level ($p < 0.05$). Taking into account the results of the Duncan test, the data were presented in tables and then interpretations were made.

3. Results

Analysis of variance and Duncan test results for the elemental contents of the materials subject to the study are given in Table 1.

Table 1 Analysis of variance and Duncan test results

Material	Pb (ppm)	Cr (ppm)	Zn (ppm)	Cd (ppm)
Fly ash	17.14f	33.02d	10.74ab	257.20a
Wood ash	9.66cd	103.67e	446.18c	444.85de
Silica fume	5.47b	5.48abc	10.19ab	440.09bc
Red Pumice	13.33e	97.66e	24.19ab	402.16de
Vermiculite	21.26g	11.95bc	23.12ab	540.59c
Brick powder	11.49de	13.40c	35.98b	498.26c
Tire powder	11.12de	2.15ab	0.00a	703.90d
Marble powder	7.63bc	2.40ab	9.64ab	684.49d
Zeolite	37.36h	8.88abc	18.31ab	352.97ab
Blast furnace slag	2.08a	1.16a	9.68ab	434.52bc
F Value	85.687***	153.386***	210.304***	19.005***

As a result of the analysis of variance, the materials differed statistically in all elements at 99.9% confidence level. As a result of Duncan test in Pb, the materials subject to the study were grouped in 8 homogeneous groups, the lowest value was obtained in blast furnace slag and the highest value was obtained in zeolite. The materials were grouped in 5 homogeneous groups in terms of Cr concentration, the lowest value was obtained in blast furnace slag and the highest values were obtained in Red Pumice and wood ash.

As a result of the analysis, the Zn concentration obtained in tire dust was below the determinable limits. As a result of the Duncan test, the materials subject to the study were grouped in 3 homogeneous groups in terms of Zn concentration, the highest value was obtained in wood ash and all other materials were in the first two groups. In terms of Cd concentration, the materials subject to the study were grouped into 4 homogeneous groups, the lowest values were obtained in Fly ash and Zeolite, and the highest values were obtained in Rubber dust, Marble dust, Red Pumice and Wood ash materials.

4. Result and Discussion

Within the scope of the study, Pb, Cr, Cd and Zn concentrations of 10 materials frequently used as concrete admixtures were determined. Heavy metals are elements whose concentrations in nature are constantly increasing and most of them are released into nature from anthropogenic sources such as mining, industry and traffic. They do not easily degrade or disappear in nature [55-59]. Therefore, heavy metal exposure and related health risks are constantly increasing and this issue is becoming more and more important every day. Due to the importance of the issue, many studies have been carried out in various fields to identify and reduce heavy metal pollution [27,29,31]. However, the number of studies on the subject in the field of civil engineering is almost negligible. However, as revealed in this study, the heavy metal content of concrete admixtures can be very high. As a result of the study, it was determined that heavy metal concentrations in the concrete admixtures subject to the study can reach up to 37.36 ppm for Pb, 103.67 ppm for Cr, 446.18 ppm for Zn and 444.85 ppm for Cd.

The values obtained as a result of the study show that they can even exceed the values obtained in traffic and industrial zones, which are shown as the main sources of heavy metal pollution. For example, in a study conducted on road dust, Cd concentration was found to vary between 2.5 ppm and 4.5 ppm [60]. Some concentrations determined in this study are much higher than this value.

It is stated that construction activities, especially in urban centers, are one of the factors that most affect the amount of particulate matter in the air during both construction and demolition [42,43]. These particulate matter act as a sink for heavy metals in urban areas. The chemical composition of particulate matter also greatly influences heavy metal pollution in air and subsequently in soil and water [18,21,54]. Therefore, concrete admixtures can pose a major risk to the health of workers in construction activities. In addition, these particles may also adversely affect the health of people and living organisms in urban areas.

As a result of the study, it was determined that there can be a significant difference between the lowest and highest values and this difference can reach hundreds of times. This result shows that the chemical content of waste materials used as concrete admixtures can be very variable. Similar results were obtained in other studies [42,43].

Recommendations

A total of 10 concrete admixtures were evaluated within the scope of the study. Most of the materials subject to the study are waste materials and the recycling of these materials contributes significantly to reducing their environmental impact. Therefore, besides the use of these materials as concrete admixtures, the possibilities of using these materials in different areas should be investigated. Some of the materials with very high concentrations of heavy metals are wastes of different sectors and therefore people working in some sectors other than the construction sector are also exposed to the dust of these materials. Other sectors where these materials are used should be warned and necessary precautions should be taken. People exposed to these materials should be made aware and precautions should be taken during work, especially in terms of inhalation.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that they no conflict of interest. The none of the authors have any competing interests in the manuscript.

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